

FINANCING OF CONSTRUCTION AND RECONSTRUCTION WORKS ON PUBLIC HIGHWAYS WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE INVESTMENT PROGRAM

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Abstract. Financing of public highways is carried out within the framework of the state investment program. In this regard, international experiences have been studied, and scientific and practical proposals have been developed to address existing problems and shortcomings in our country.

Key words: Public use, highways, investment program, financing, construction, reconstruction.

Introduction

It is impossible to increase a country's economic potential without investment. As a result of investment, industrial enterprises develop actively, and gross domestic product grows. The country's activity in foreign markets increases. In major economic processes, investments play an important role not only at the national level, but also at the level of sectors and individual enterprises. Practice shows that investment risk is closely linked to a country's production potential. The scale and effectiveness of the investment process predetermine the resolution of many social issues, including improving living standards, reducing unemployment, and enhancing working conditions.

Literature review

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, investments in the road sector include the construction of new automobile roads, their reconstruction, technical re-equipment, and maintenance of existing roads.

Among national economists, F. Dodiev defines the concept of investment as follows: "Investment refers to the total of all types of tangible, financial, and intellectual wealth that investors allocate to entrepreneurial activity objects with the aim of gaining future profit (income) or achieving social benefit."

Another economist, N. Haydarov, states: "Regardless of the form of ownership, investment is the allocation of financial, material, and intellectual resources available to individuals, legal entities, or the state to any entrepreneurial object for the purpose of achieving economic and social outcomes within the legal framework."

S.V. Shkodinsky interprets investment as: "A part of socially produced goods created and preserved in monetary, material, and intangible forms,

aimed at increasing the quantity and quality of production factors used in various fields of entrepreneurship.”

Investments can be categorized as follows:

1. State – formed through the state budget and public financial sources;
2. Foreign – made by foreign investors, including other countries, international banks, companies, and entrepreneurs;
3. Private – formed through private and corporate enterprises, organizations, and citizens' own and borrowed funds.

Currently, construction and reconstruction of public highways are being carried out in our Republic based on the state investment program funded by the state budget.

It is important to note that road construction includes the technological, infrastructural, and managerial processes required to build a road. Meanwhile, reconstruction refers to a set of activities that alter road parameters and segments, which may result in a change of road category and/or class or a modification of the road's right-of-way boundaries.

Information on the Dynamics of Road Lengths Constructed and Reconstructed, and Allocated Funds within the Framework of the Investment Program from the State Budget for the Years 2020–2024 ¹

Year	Length of reconstructed road (km)	Growth rate %		Amount spent (billion soums)	Growth rate %	
		Basic Compared to 2020	Compared to previous years		Basic Compared to 2020	Compared to previous years
A	1	2	3	4	5	6
2020	105,9	100	100	924,8	100	100
2021	125,5	118,5	118,5	1686,0	182,3	182,3
2022	130,1	122,8	103,7	1682,1	181,9	99,8
2023	142,1	134,2	109,2	1138,1	123,0	67,7
2024	133,0	125,6	93,6	1427,1	154,3	125,4

Source: Independently prepared by the researcher based on the information of the Highways Committee.

The shortest length of roads reconstructed under the investment program from the state budget was recorded in 2020 at 105.9 km, while the longest was

¹Data from the Highways Committee.

in 2023 at 142.1 km. This accounted for 0.25% of the total public road network in 2020 and 0.33% in 2023.

Over the period under review, this indicator averaged 1.5% relative to the total road length. If we consider that the total length of roads reconstructed from state budget funds within the investment program between 2020 and 2024 amounted to 636.6 km, the average annual length of reconstructed roads was 127.32 km.

In addition, the dynamics of reconstructed road lengths over the years were studied using the **base method**. In 2020, 105.9 km of roads were reconstructed under the investment program. This figure increased to 133 km in 2024, which means an increase of 27.1 km compared to the base year, with a growth rate of 125.6%.

Using the **chain method**, 142.1 km of roads were reconstructed in 2023, and 133 km in 2024. A comparison between these two years shows that in 2024, 9.1 km fewer roads were reconstructed, indicating a decrease of 6.4% in the dynamics.

The dynamics of funds allocated for public highways under the investment program from 2020 to 2024 were also examined. The highest amount of funding compared to the base year was allocated in 2021, totaling 1,686.0 billion UZS—761.2 billion UZS more than in 2020, or a growth rate of 182.3%.

Based on the **chain method**, the year with the lowest amount allocated was 2023, totaling 1,138.1 billion UZS. In comparison, 1,682.1 billion UZS were allocated in 2022, meaning the funding in 2023 was 544.0 billion UZS less, or 67.7% of the previous year's figure.

The dynamics of state budget allocations under the investment program show a **base growth rate** of 154.3% in 2024, and a **chain growth rate** of 125.4% compared to 2023.

Conclusion

Forming a road network that meets the needs of the population ensures the free movement of goods and services, and allows people, goods, works, and services to be delivered safely and efficiently to the required destinations in a timely and high-quality manner.

Investments in automobile roads are closely tied to income-generating activities. Analyzing investments dynamically allows for the integration of resources, investment volumes, and investment profitability. Therefore, it is recommended to direct any investment that yields economic returns into road infrastructure development.

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